

Low Complexity Soft Demapper for MIMO Sidelink Communications

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Abstract— The Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has introduced definitions and services for 5G New Radio (NR) V2X since Release 16 to provide promising technology standards for future automotive driving. In this paper, we present an optimized soft demapper that exploits information from multiple layers, instead of a single layer, to improve the performance of the algorithm while maintaining a low implementation complexity. The Block Error Rate (BLER) performance of the proposed soft demapping method is evaluated through link-level simulations of the 5G NR Physical Sidelink Shared Channel (PSSCH). Different modulation schemes and multipath fading channel conditions were simulated to evaluate the performance of the proposed soft demapper. Simulation results show a performance improvement in terms of BLER vs SNR compared to state-of-the-art methods.

Keywords—soft demapper, 3GPP, LLRs, sidelink, LDPC

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing demand for fully automated mobility and public safety services, wireless communication has become the fundamental aspect for entering the new era, which is distinguished by numerous vehicles, pedestrians, and other road elements. For bringing vehicular communications to commercial usage under the Vehicle to Everything (V2X) scenario, the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has been dedicated to introducing sidelink communication into 5G New Radio (NR) standards in Release 16 via PC5 interface, which is so-called “5G-V2X” [1]. Later, in Release 17 and Release 18, sidelink was further enhanced to introduce more V2X applications.

Based on the latest 3GPP standards, different modulation schemes can be configured to sidelink communication to deal with different deployment scenarios. The standard specifications allow the use of up to 64 QAM modulation, via the corresponding Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) and pre configured tables, so as to provide high spectral efficiency [2]. Although a higher modulation scheme for a given bandwidth can provide higher data rates, it also increases the complexity of the demodulation part with the traditional log-

domain maximum a posteriori probability (Log-MAP) demapping algorithm [3]. In [4], the authors proposed the maximum approximation of Log-MAP (Max-Log-MAP) to reduce the computation complexity. However, the order of computational complexity still remains at $O(2^m)$, where m is the number of bits per symbol and 2^m is the size of the constellation.

Lots of algorithms have been studied for simplifying the Max-Log-MAP algorithm. By partitioning the 2^m -ary QAM constellation into two separate constellations, one for the in-phase component and another for the quadrature component, each with $2^{\frac{m}{2}}$ -ary Pulse Amplitude Modulation (PAM), the computational complexity of the associated Max-Log-MAP demapper is reduced from $O(2^m)$ to $O(2^{\frac{m}{2}})$ [5]. The algorithm described in [6] efficiently identifies the two necessary constellation points to calculate a single LLR. The algorithms detailed in [7] and [8] share remarkable similarities, offering a straightforward method for computing LLRs. In [9], through the utilization of the symmetry property present in Gray-labelled constellations, the complexity of the demapper is further reduced to $O(m)$ without any performance degradation. Following the method in [7] and [9], the authors of [10] expand it into 256 QAM for 5G mobile systems.

The soft demapping derivations in the above mentioned studies considered mainly single-layer transmission scenarios. This paper proposes a novel method that considers the effect of multiple transmitted layers into the soft demapping process. The performance of the optimized algorithm is then evaluated with link level simulations for the Physical Sidelink Shared Channel (PSSCH) defined by the 3GPP standard 5G NR sidelink for various modulation schemes and under different fading channel scenarios. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the structure of the physical layer for the sidelink and a brief overview of the MIMO system model employed for the derivations. Section III presents the analytical derivations of the proposed soft demapper algorithm for demodulating PSSCH sidelink signals. Section IV presents the results obtained through simulations.

Finally, Section V summarizes the conclusions drawn from the study.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Workflow for sidelink physical layer

Figure 1 illustrates the sidelink MIMO OFDM system model employed in this paper for deriving the proposed soft demapper.

From the transmitter, bitstream m is encoded by the LDPC encoder and polar encoder defined in the 3GPP specifications for PSSCH data and 2nd stage Sidelink Control Information (SCI) respectively and generates codeword c . The bit length permutation value determines how c is interleaved. After going through the interleaver, c_{init} is fed into the mapper where bits are mapped to complex QAM symbols according to the configured modulation resulting in the complex symbol stream $X(N)$. N represents the number of subcarriers as well as the inverse fast Fourier transform (iFFT) size. The way in which complex symbols map to subcarriers in $X(N)$ depends on the subcarrier allocation of the configured sidelink transmission. Then, the symbol stream $X(N)$ is converted into N parallel symbols through the serial-to-parallel converter. The iFFT is then applied to generate the time domain orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) symbol $x(0), x(1), \dots, x(N-1)$. A configurable size cyclic prefix (CP) is then padded to the beginning of the OFDM symbol to combat inter symbol interference (ISI). The resulting signal is then sent through the channel model and impaired with additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) n . In the receiver, the CP is removed followed by a fast Fourier transform (FFT) to convert the signal from time domain to frequency domain. The resulting frequency domain signal $Y(0), Y(1), \dots, Y(N-1)$ goes through parallel-to-serial conversion and is fed into the equalizer module. Inside the equalizer, the channel frequency response is estimated and compensated for. The equalized signal Z is then input to the proposed soft demapper where the soft information for every transmitted bit in the form of log-likelihood ratios (LLRs) is estimated. Finally, the soft bits λ are de-interleaved and decoded accordingly based on LDPC decoder and polar decoder to restore information bits.

B. MIMO system model

Since the sidelink allows for a maximum of two layer transmission, in this section, we present a MIMO OFDM system model for deriving the proposed soft demapper.

At the receiver side, the received vector after the FFT process, assuming no ISI, can be modelled as:

$$Y(k) = H(k)X(k) + n(k); k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1, \quad (1)$$

where, for the rest of the section, k represents the subcarrier index. $X(k) = [X_1(k), X_2(k), \dots, X_{n_T}(k)]^T$ is a $n_T \times 1$ vector of modulated symbols where n_T denotes the number of transmit antennas. $Y(k) = [Y_1(k), Y_2(k), \dots, Y_{n_R}(k)]^T$, is a

Fig. 1. System model for sidelink transmitter and receiver

$n_R \times 1$ vector where n_R denotes the number of receive antennas. $n[k] = [n_1(k), n_2(k), \dots, n_{n_R}(k)]^T$ is a $n_R \times 1$ vector representing AWGN whose covariance matrix is modelled as $R_{nn} = \sigma^2 I$. $H(k)$ represents the $n_R \times n_T$ MIMO channel frequency response (CFR) matrix for the k^{th} subcarrier which can be written as:

$$H(k) = \begin{bmatrix} h_{11}(k) & \dots & h_{1n_T}(k) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ h_{n_R1}(k) & \dots & h_{n_Rn_T}(k) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Each element of $H(k)$ should be an independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) random variable. Assuming error-free channel estimation, the equalizer can compensate for the MIMO channel impairment. Hence, the equalized $n_T \times 1$ vector signal becomes

$$Z(k) = H^\dagger(k)Y(k) = X(k) + H^\dagger(k)n(k) \quad (3)$$

where $H^\dagger(k)n(k)$ is an $n_T \times 1$ dimensional multivariate Gaussian complex random variable representing the AWGN after equalization, and $H^\dagger(k)$ represents pseudo inverse of the CFR matrix. To statistically characterize $Z(k)$, we now recall the definition of the probability density function (PDF) of a normal k -dimensional multivariate complex random variable $X = [X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k]$ as

$$pdf(X) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{k/2} \det(\Sigma)^{1/2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(X-\mu)^T(\Sigma)^{-1}(X-\mu)} \quad (4)$$

Where μ represents the k -dimensional mean vector and Σ denotes the $k \times k$ covariance matrix. For the case where the components of X are independent with each other and have zero mean $\mu = \bar{0}$, Σ and Σ^{-1} become diagonal and the pdf can be expressed as

$$pdf(X) = \prod_i \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{ii}}} e^{-\frac{\|X_i\|^2}{2\sigma_{ii}}} \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma_{ii} = \sigma_i^2$ represents the (i,i) diagonal entry of Σ .

III. PROPOSED SOFT DEMAPPER ALGORITHM

In this section, we propose an algorithm for extracting the soft information of each of the bits carried in any QAM modulation supported in the 5G NR sidelink standard. In the following, the highest modulation scheme supported in the sidelink, 64QAM, is taken as example for the derivations while the application of the presented method to other modulations is straightforward.

A. First step: Approximation of LLR calculation

As we all know, in the receiver part, the bit level demapping can be performed either as “hard” or “soft”. The former one, called “hard decision”, uses a logical value of 1 or 0 to indicate result. In contrast, the “soft decision” uses the log-likelihood ratio (LLR) to imply the probability of a demapping decision to be of logical value 1 or 0. Based on the equation from [7], the expression of LLR can be written as:

$$LLR(b_{k,v}^j | Y(k), H(k)) = \ln \frac{p(Z(k) | b_{k,v}^j = 1)}{p(Z(k) | b_{k,v}^j = 0)} \quad (6)$$

where $b_{k,v}^j$ is the transmitted information bit in the k^{th} subcarrier, v^{th} layer and j^{th} bit. Denote by X_j^1 the set of symbols for a given QAM constellation having a “1” in the j^{th} bit. Similarly, denote by X_j^0 the set of symbols for a given QAM constellation having a “0” in the j^{th} bit. Since Z is a multi-dimensional random variable, plugging (5) into (6), we have the LLR value can be derived as:

$$\begin{aligned} LLR(b_{k,v}^j | Y(k), H(k)) &= \ln \frac{\sum_{X(k) \rightarrow X_v \in X_j^1} \prod_i \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{ii}}} e^{-\frac{\|Y(k) - H(k)X(k)\|^2}{2\sigma_{ii}}}}{\sum_{X(k) \rightarrow X_v \in X_j^0} \prod_i \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{ii}}} e^{-\frac{\|Y(k) - H(k)X(k)\|^2}{2\sigma_{ii}}}} \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

For clarification, $X(k) \rightarrow X_v \in X_j^1$ means all possible transmitted vector arrays in subcarrier index k whose j^{th} bit in the v^{th} layer array position is a logical “1”. Applying the Bayes theorem and the log-sum-exponential approximation in [4], the calculation of LLR can then be further simplified to:

$$\begin{aligned} LLR(b_{k,v}^j | Y(k), H(k)) &= \max_{X(k) \rightarrow X_v \in X_j^1} \left[-\frac{\|H(k)(Z(k) - X(k))\|^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \right] \\ &\quad - \max_{X(k) \rightarrow X_v \in X_j^0} \left[-\frac{\|H(k)(Z(k) - X(k))\|^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \min_{X(k) \rightarrow X_v \in X_j^0} \left[\frac{\|H(k)(Z(k) - X(k))\|^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \right] \\ &\quad - \min_{X(k) \rightarrow X_v \in X_j^1} \left[\frac{\|H(k)(Z(k) - X(k))\|^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \right] \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

Expression (8) is still computationally demanding and further simplifications are required for an efficient implementation of the algorithm. For ease of notation, consider $\bar{a} = Z(k) - X(k)$ and equation (8) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} &LLR(b_{k,v}^j | Y(k), H(k)) \\ &= \min_{X(k) \rightarrow X_v \in X_j^0} \left[\frac{\|H(k)\bar{a}\|^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \right] - \min_{X(k) \rightarrow X_v \in X_j^1} \left[\frac{\|H(k)\bar{a}\|^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \right] \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

Since $H(k)$ is not a scalar, it cannot be taken out of the norm. We now expand the $H(k)\bar{a}$ multiplication. In sidelink communications, the maximum number of layers that can be employed is 2 [11]. Therefore, assuming a 2x2 channel frequency response matrix as an example, the $H(k)\bar{a}$ matrix multiplication is expanded as:

$$\begin{aligned} H(k)\bar{a} &= \begin{bmatrix} h_{11}(k) & h_{12}(k) \\ h_{21}(k) & h_{22}(k) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} h_{11}(k)a_1 + h_{12}(k)a_2 \\ h_{21}(k)a_1 + h_{22}(k)a_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\|H(k)\bar{a}\|^2$ will be:

$$\begin{aligned} \|H(k)\bar{a}\|^2 &= \|h_{11}(k)a_1 + h_{12}(k)a_2\|^2 \\ &\quad + \|h_{21}(k)a_1 + h_{22}(k)a_2\|^2 \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

where $\|*\|$ denotes the Frobenius norm. In order to further simplify (9) we take the following approximation. Since the minimization in (9) is done over the v^{th} layer, we neglect the contribution of other layers different than v in the $\|H(k)\bar{a}\|^2$ matrix multiplication and thus, for the v^{th} layer:

$$\min_{X(k) \rightarrow X_v \in X_j^{0,1}} \|H(k)\bar{a}\|^2 \approx \left(\sum_{r=1}^{n_R} \|h_{r,v}(k)\|^2 \right) a_v \quad (12)$$

Under this approximation, equation (8) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} &LLR(b_{k,v}^j | Y(k), H(k)) \\ &= \sum_{r=1}^{n_R} \frac{\|h_{r,v}(k)\|^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \left(\min_{X_v \in X_j^0} [Z_v(k) - X_v(k)]^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \min_{X_v \in X_j^1} [Z_v(k) - X_v(k)]^2 \right) \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

It is noted that the first term in the above equation scales the LLRs by the norm of the v^{th} column of the estimated MIMO channel matrix.

B. Second step: Compute Euclidean distance

In the case of a 64QAM modulation, each symbol includes six bits $m_0, m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4, m_5$, where the real part of the received symbol corresponds to bits m_0, m_1, m_2 , while the imaginary part of the received symbol corresponds to bits

m_3, m_4, m_5 . The normalization factor for the 64QAM modulation is $M = 1/\sqrt{42}$. With this normalization factor, both in-phase and quadrature are normalized to eight possible values: $\{-7M, -5M, -3M, -1M, 1M, 3M, 5M, 7M\}$. Following the decomposition of 256QAM modulation mentioned in [10], the 64QAM can similarly be decomposed into its in-phase and quadrature dimensions as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. In-Phase and Quadrature decomposition for 64QAM

Denote

$$\theta(m_j) = \min_{X_v \in X_j^0} [Z_v(k) - X_v(k)]^2 - \min_{X_v \in X_j^1} [Z_v(k) - X_v(k)]^2 \quad (14)$$

Then,

$$LLR(b_{k,v}^j | Y(k), H(k)) = \sum_{r=1}^{n_R} \frac{\|h_{r,v}(k)\|^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \theta(m_j) \quad (15)$$

For illustration, assume a received and equalized 64QAM symbol Z_v in the v^{th} layer. Assume now we want to compute the LLR corresponding to bit m_0 of that layer and $Re\{Z_v\}$ denotes the real part of received symbol Z_v . According to Fig 2, bit m_0 belongs to the In-phase axis. m_0 maps to 0 if $Re\{Z_v\} \in \{-7M, -5M, -3M, -1M\}$, while m_0 maps to 1 if $Re\{Z_v\} \in \{1M, 3M, 5M, 7M\}$. Assuming $Re\{Z_v\}$ falls into interval: $Re\{Z_v\} < -6M$, the nearest point that makes m_0 map to 0 is $X_v(k) = -7M$. Similarly, the nearest point that makes m_0 map to 1 is $X_v(k) = M$. Thus, $\theta(m_0)$ is computed as:

$$\theta(m_0) = [Re\{Z_v\} - (-7M)]^2 - [Re\{Z_v\} - M]^2 = 16M(Re\{Z_v\} + 3M) \quad (16)$$

Substituting the value of $\theta(m_0)$ into (15), then

$$LLR(b_{k,v}^0) = \left(\sum_{r=1}^{n_R} \|h_{r,v}(k)\|^2 \right) 16M(Re\{Z_v\} + 3M) \quad (17)$$

Where the noise variance has been neglected as we assume the same noise variance across all subcarriers. In fact, it is noted that the term $\frac{4M}{2\sigma_i^2}$ is common to all $\theta(m_j)$ cases and, without loss of generality, it is hence neglected in the derivations.

C. LLR derivation for each bit

The derivation of $\theta(m_j)$ corresponding to the rest of the bits belonging to the In-phase axis in Fig 2 is similarly

computed and it is summarized in Table I.

TABLE I LLR FOR EACH BIT

Bit index	Expression of $\theta(m_j)$	Range of detected bit
m_0	$4(Re\{Z_v\} + 3M)$ $3(Re\{Z_v\} + 2M)$ $2(Re\{Z_v\} + M)$ $Re\{Z_v\}$ $-2(Re\{Z_v\} - M)$ $-3(Re\{Z_v\} - 2M)$ $-4(Re\{Z_v\} - 3M)$	$Re\{Z_v\} < -6M$ $-6M \leq Re\{Z_v\} < -4M$ $-4M \leq Re\{Z_v\} < -2M$ $-2M \leq Re\{Z_v\} < 2M$ $2M \leq Re\{Z_v\} < 4M$ $4M \leq Re\{Z_v\} < 6M$ $Re\{Z_v\} \geq 6M$
m_1	$-2(Re\{Z_v\} + 5M)$ $-(Re\{Z_v\} + 4M)$ $-2(Re\{Z_v\} + 3M)$ $-2(Re\{Z_v\} - 3M)$ $Re\{Z_v\} - 4M$ $2(Re\{Z_v\} - 5M)$	$Re\{Z_v\} < -6M$ $-6M \leq Re\{Z_v\} < -2M$ $-2M \leq Re\{Z_v\} < 0$ $0 \leq Re\{Z_v\} < 2M$ $2M \leq Re\{Z_v\} < 6M$ $Re\{Z_v\} \geq 6M$
m_2	$Re\{Z_v\} + 6M$ $-(Re\{Z_v\} + 2M)$ $Re\{Z_v\} + 2M$ $-(Re\{Z_v\} - 6M)$	$Re\{Z_v\} < -4M$ $-4M \leq Re\{Z_v\} < 0$ $0 \leq Re\{Z_v\} < 4M$ $Re\{Z_v\} \geq 4M$

With the expressions for $\theta(m_j)$, the final LLR values for each bit are obtained accordingly by scaling $\theta(m_j)$ with the v -th column norm of the estimated MIMO channel matrix as stated in equation (17).

Following the same steps from A to C, the LLR derivations of bits m_3, m_4, m_5 can be simply computed based on the imaginary part of the equalized QAM symbol. From Fig 2, it is noted that the in-phase and quadrature bit distribution of the QAM constellation is symmetrical. Thus, the expressions of $\theta(m_j)$ for bits m_3, m_4, m_5 are the same as bits m_0, m_1, m_2 . Assuming the imaginary part of Z_v is $Im\{Z_v\}$, substituting $Re\{Z_v\}$ with $Im\{Z_v\}$ in Table I allows for the straightforward computation of $\theta(m_j)$ and LLRs for the m_3, m_4, m_5 bits. Although shown for a 64QAM, this method can be easily adapted to other modulations. To be noted, the simplicity of the calculations is evident in Table I, where it is clear that all the computations just involve basic operations, resulting in very low complexity. Meanwhile, these calculations do not necessitate minimization searches or the computation of Euclidean distances.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed method, we conducted link level simulations for a 5G NR sidelink system.

In our simulations, we examined the PSSCH channel of a sidelink communication equipped with up to two transmit antennas and two receive antennas. All simulations were conducted under a 100 MHz channel bandwidth. The MIMO channel, which was modeled in accordance with TDL channel models defined in 3GPP standards [12], is composed of multiple delay paths each with its own gain. We conducted simulations with different numbers of channel and noise realizations for different modulation schemes. On the receiving end, perfect timing and frequency synchronizations were assumed prior to estimating the MIMO channel. Then,

we computed the bit LLRs employing two methods for comparison. Firstly, the proposed method which considers the v^{th} norm of the estimated MIMO channel matrix as in equation (17) is shown. Secondly, a general zero-forcing method which does not consider the MIMO channel matrix in the LLR derivations is simulated. Thirdly, the Max-Log-MAP algorithm with neglecting noise impact is simulated as well as benchmark. The performances of all the three methods are compared by counting the number of correct PSSCH CRCs in each simulated slot. After counting the number of correct PSSCH CRCs in each slot, this count was stored. This process was iterated for a user-configurable number of slots. The final Block Error Rate (BLER) was determined by dividing the total count of properly received PSSCH CRCs by the overall number of codewords generated throughout all the slots in each simulation. The performance of the novel PSSCH receiver structure with the proposed soft demapper is evaluated in terms of BLER versus Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) graphs. All the details regarding the simulation parameters are summarized in TABLE II.

Fig. 3 shows the BLER versus SNR performance of the proposed soft demapper for a 64QAM PSSCH transmission with MCS 20, having 3.3223 of spectral efficiency with a 0.5537 of code rate. The channel model employed for this simulation is TDLA30-10 determined by specifications, where 30 is RMS delay spread in ns, and 10 is the maximum doppler frequency in Hz. We compared the performance of the proposed method against a general soft demapper algorithm which does not scale LLRs based on the MIMO channel matrix. Meanwhile, the conventional Max-Log-MAP method is also compared with the proposed method. As shown in Fig. 3, our method exhibits an approximate performance improvement of ~ 3 dB compared to the alternative approaches.

Fig. 4 provides simulation results for another case under TDLC300-100 channel model, with 300ns delay spread and maximum 100Hz doppler frequency. Under this scenario, the channel changes faster than TDLA30-10 model, thus, to achieve the same BLER, this particular test needs higher SNR. In this scenario, it is worth noting that an error floor becomes evident. The error floor observed may be attributed to imperfect channel estimation. Since the channel in this situation exhibits faster variations compared to the previous one, accurately tracking the channel becomes challenging. Meanwhile, only 2 DMRS symbols are employed in this configuration, considering the fast change of channel, it might not be adequate to estimate the channel. On the other side, this error floor could be caused by ISI since we are using multipath channel model. Consequently, despite increasing the SNR, there may be limited improvement in the BLER. However, the proposed optimized soft demapper algorithm still offers a better performance with a 5dB increment. To be noticed, the reason that those error floors of two simulations are not converging is because different methods introduce different noises to the LDPC decoder, thus they have different levels of error floors.

TABLE II SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Simulation parameter	Configured value
Carrier frequency/GHz	3.5016
Bandwidth/MHz	100
Numerology μ	1
Subcarrier spacing/kHz	30
FFT size	4096
Number of DMRS symbols	2
Number of simulation slots	1500/500
Channel type	TDL model
Number of configured RBs	260
Number of PSSCH symbols	12
Modulation Scheme	16QAM/64QAM
MCS Index	16/20
Code rate	0.6426/0.5537
Iterations of LDPC decoder	8

Fig. 3. BLER vs. SNR for TDLA 30-10 model, 2T2R of different methods, MCS20, 64QAM

Fig. 4. BLER vs. SNR for TDLC 300-100 model, 2T2R of different methods, MCS20, 64QAM

Fig. 5 shows the performance test result with the same channel condition employed in Fig. 3, yet with a different modulation scheme and code rate. MCS 16, 2.5703 of spectral efficiency, and 0.6426 of code rate are utilized for this test case. The figure shows that a lower modulation scheme requires a lower SNR to accomplish the same performance. Meanwhile, compared with the result without scaling by multilayer channel response and the conventional Max-Log-MAP algorithm, the proposed method depicts 1dB enhancement. This demonstrates that this method is adaptable to a wide range of modulation schemes and is not restricted to a specific design.

Fig. 5. BLER vs. SNR for TDLA 30-10 model, 2T2R of different methods, MCS16, 16QAM

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented an optimized soft demapper of various modulation schemes for 5G NR V2X sidelink communication, delivering soft LLRs for improved decoder performance. In the newly proposed algorithm, we account for the influence of the MIMO estimated channel and leverage multi-layer data to adjust the LLR values, enhancing the precision of soft value estimation while maintaining low computational complexity. A detailed derivation of all the formulas involved in the LLR calculation has been provided. The performance improvement of the proposed method has been verified through PSSCH sidelink simulations which strictly follow the 3GPP standard. Under this test environment, we have conducted simulations with different test parameters for BLER performance. The simulation outcomes validate that the proposed algorithm significantly

enhances the performance compared to a state-of-art algorithm and demonstrates robustness across a broad range of modulation schemes and fading channels.

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